

FLOODPLAIN LIVING ENVIRONMENT - A DYNAMIC WORLD

TEACHING PROTOCOL

GRADE LEVEL: Secondary School

LESSON STRUCTURE: 1 school lesson (45 min.) for the introduction (ENGAGE),
2 lessons (90-100 min.) for field observations – ideally outdoors (EXPLORE),
1 lesson (45 min.) for linking adaptations and processes (EXPLAIN),
1-2 lessons (45-50 min) for applying knowledge and designing sustainable
management scenarios (ELABORATE),
1 lesson (45 min.) for reflection and creative synthesis (EVALUATE).

INTRODUCTION:

Floodplains are low-lying areas along rivers that are regularly flooded by the river, making them one of the most dynamic ecosystems on Earth. Their shape and vegetation are continually reshaped by **flooding, erosion, and sediment deposition**, creating a patchwork of aquatic and terrestrial habitats that regularly changes over time.

Organisms in floodplains have developed special **adaptations** to survive these shifts: floodplain plants usually tolerate waterlogging and shifting soils, while animals migrate, burrow, or breed in rhythm with floods. These adaptations reveal how life may thrive amid constant change.

In this lesson, students will explore how floodplains function as living, moving systems, discover how species adapt to them, and reflect on how humans can coexist with these dynamic environments.

LEARNING OBJECTIVES:

By the end of this lesson, students will be able to:

- 1 Explain how natural processes shape floodplain habitats.
- 2 Identify adaptive traits of plants and animals living in dynamic environments.
- 3 Understand human impacts on floodplain ecosystems.
- 4 Evaluate trade-offs between flood safety, economy, and ecology.
- 5 Propose balanced solutions for living with floods.

TEACHING FRAMEWORK BASED ON THE 5E INSTRUCTIONAL MODEL

1. ENGAGE - Sparking curiosity (45 minutes)

AIM: To spark curiosity about floodplain dynamics and the life adapted to them. Students realize how floods, erosion, and vegetation create an ever-changing landscape and reflect on what it means to live in such a place.

KEYWORDS: hydrological dynamics, geomorphological dynamics, ecological dynamics, vegetation succession

ACTIVITY 1: "DISCOVERING A RIVER IN MOTION"

Watch a short time-lapse video or animation showing a floodplain changing through the seasons — floods, erosion, sedimentation, and vegetation regrowth.

GUIDING QUESTIONS

- What changes can you see during and after floods?
- Where does the water go when the flood recedes?
- How does the shape of the river and surrounding land change?
- Which areas look suitable for different types of life?

TEACHER SUPPORT:

Explain briefly how hydrology (moving water) shapes landforms (meanders, oxbow lakes), which in turn support diverse ecological communities (plants, fish, insects, birds).

Emphasize that floodplains are not static — they are shaped by cycles of disturbance and renewal. Use [Annex 1](#) for supplementary documentation on *Floodplains Dynamics*.

ACTIVITY 2: "WHO LIVES HERE"

In pairs or groups, observe a set of photos showing floodplain plants and animals. Guess where each plant and animal might live — in water, on land, or both — and how they survive floods or droughts.

GUIDING QUESTIONS

- What kinds of organisms can you identify?
- Where do they live — in the water, on land, or between both?
- How might floods affect their way of living or finding food?
- How do they cope with changes in water levels?

TEACHER SUPPORT:

- Provide printed or projected images of plants and animals from floodplains, e.g. birds, fish, amphibians, willow, sedges, dragonflies.
- Highlight adaptations such as roots that tolerate waterlogging, animals that migrate, or species that breed during floods. Use the *Wetland-Education Repository of Restore4Life* for supplementary documentation.

ACTIVITY 3: USE THE INTERACTIVE VISUALIZATION – RESTORE4LIFE “FLOODPLAIN LIVING ENVIRONMENT”

Students explore the online tool and discuss what makes floodplains both risky and rich in life.

2. EXPLORE – Hands-on learning activity (90–100 min, ideally outdoors near a river, wetland)

AIM: To observe, investigate, and experience how floodplain species and habitats respond to changing water levels and environmental conditions.

In this phase, students explore a nearby floodplain-like environment or a wetland area, or a schoolyard simulation (if field access is limited). Through guided observation, discussion, and role-based games, they learn how flooding, erosion, and sedimentation shape the land — and how living organisms adapt to these natural forces.

KEYWORDS: waterlogging, waterproof, plant aerenchyma tissues, rhizome network, stolon, high fecundity, breeding flexibility, germination, eurytopic species, specialist species.

ACTIVITY 1 – EXPLORING THE LIVING FLOODPLAIN (FIELD OBSERVATION)

AIM: To observe how water, land, and living organisms shape and depend on each other in a dynamic environment.

INSTRUCTIONS FOR STUDENTS:

Walk slowly through the area in small groups. Look around and notice how the land changes — low areas, small ponds, ridges, or patches of vegetation.

Discuss what might happen here during a flood and what traces the water leaves behind.

Observe plants and animals and think about how they might cope with flooding or dry periods.

Share interesting observations/photos with the class (e.g., “We saw plants with roots above ground”, “There was driftwood showing how far the water reached”).

GUIDING QUESTIONS

- What signs show that this area has been flooded before?
- Which places seem wetter or drier, and why?
- What kinds of plants and animals do you see, and how might they survive floods?
- What might happen here when the river floods again?

TEACHER SUPPORT:

- Before the visit, briefly introduce how floods create a mosaic of habitats. During the walk, stop at a few key spots (e.g., eroded bank, wet meadow, pool) and ask guiding questions. Encourage observation with all senses — look, listen, smell, and feel the soil. Take a few photos together to use later in the Explain step.
- Emphasize that floodplains are dynamic, constantly changing between wet and dry conditions that support different forms of life.

ACTIVITY 2 – “FLOODPLAIN HEROES” ROLE GAME

Where: Classroom or open space (indoors or outdoors)

Duration: ~45 minutes

AIM: To help students understand how plants and animals in floodplains adapt to changing water levels, disturbances, and environmental conditions.

Through a simulation game, students experience survival strategies and learn why biodiversity and adaptability are essential for ecosystem resilience.

Students take on the roles of various floodplain species — from willows and reeds to frogs, fish, and herons.

As environmental events such as floods, droughts, or sediment deposition occur, each player must decide how their organism responds based on its adaptations.

Through gameplay, students see that species respond differently to the same environmental changes, and that survival depends on the diversity of adaptations within the ecosystem.

INSTRUCTIONS FOR STUDENTS: Each player or group receives a Species Card (organism name, short description, habitat type). The teacher reads or draws Event Cards (e.g., Flood, Drought, Erosion, Sediment deposition).

For each event, students decide how their species reacts using one or more Adaptation options (e.g., burrowing, floating seeds, tolerance to waterlogging).

Based on the response, species gain or lose points — survival earns points, inability to adapt loses life points. After several rounds (5–6 events), the most resilient species becomes the “Floodplain Hero”.

GUIDING QUESTIONS

- Which adaptations helped your species survive certain events?
- Why did some species disappear earlier than others?
- What would happen to the floodplain if all species reacted in the same way?
- How does biodiversity increase the resilience of an ecosystem?
- What parallels can you see with human adaptation to floods?

TEACHER SUPPORT:

- Prepare the game materials: Species Cards, Adaptation Cards, Event Cards, Worksheets, and a simple map of the floodplain (with zones such as river, wet meadow, forest edge). Use Annex 2 for supplementary documentation on How Animals and Plants Adapt to the Dynamics of Floodplains.
- Before playing, explain the idea of adaptation and disturbance in dynamic ecosystems.
- Facilitate discussion after each event — ask students to justify their decisions and describe ecological interactions.
- After the game, lead a reflection on why diversity of traits helps ecosystems recover after disturbances.

3. EXPLAIN – Making sense of the experiences (45 minutes indoor)

AIM: To deepen students' understanding of the adaptation skills of floodplain species and how these traits help them survive in a constantly changing environment.

By linking plants and animals with their specific adaptations and environmental events, students begin to recognize patterns and relationships within floodplain ecosystems.

After exploring and playing the Floodplain Heroes game, students now reflect on what they have experienced.

Through the Mix & Match activity, they identify which species have which adaptations — and how those adaptations help them survive floods, droughts, and other natural disturbances.

This analytical step strengthens conceptual understanding by showing that adaptations are shared across species and that each trait has multiple ecological functions.

KEYWORDS: waterlogging, aerenchyma tissues, germination, rhizome network, stolon, high fecundity, breeding flexibility, eurytopic species, waterproof

ACTIVITY – MIX & MATCH: “WHO ADAPTS HOW?”

INSTRUCTIONS FOR STUDENTS:

Work in small groups or as a class.

On the board or on large flipchart sheets, there are:

- Species cards or pictures (e.g., *Lutra lutra* – European otter, *Salix alba* – white willow, *Nymphaea alba* – white water lily).
- Adaptation cards (e.g., Floating seeds, Burrowing, Aerenchyma tissue, Waterproof fur, Flexible stems, Rapid germination).
- Event cards (e.g., Flood, Drought, Erosion, Sediment deposition).

Students draw lines connecting each species to its possible adaptations.

Add one environmental event (e.g., Flood) and draw lines showing which adaptations are useful in that event.

Compare and discuss overlaps — many species share similar adaptations that serve multiple functions.

GUIDING QUESTIONS

- Can one adaptation belong to more than one species?
- How do these adaptations help in different environmental events?
- Which traits are specific to aquatic organisms, and which belong to terrestrial ones?
- Why are such diverse adaptations necessary in a floodplain ecosystem?

TEACHER SUPPORT:

- Conduct the activity on the board, flipchart, or large paper sheets. You may use printed animal and plant pictures or draw simple icons.
- Encourage discussion and justification for each connection made. Highlight that adaptations can have overlapping functions — for instance, burrowing helps against both drought and floods.
- Summarize by creating a web of connections showing how species, adaptations, and events are interlinked. Reinforce key ecological insight: biodiversity and functional variety are what keep floodplains resilient.

MATERIALS NEEDED:

Flipchart or whiteboard; colored markers or string for drawing connections; printed or hand-drawn pictures of floodplain animals and plants; adaptation and event cards

4. EXTEND / ELABORATE – Expanding understanding (45–50 minutes)

AIM:

To apply the knowledge about natural adaptations and dynamics of floodplains to human contexts — exploring how people, too, can adapt to and benefit from natural floodplain processes through sustainable management and Nature-Based Solutions (NbS).

After discovering how plants and animals survive and thrive in changing floodplain environments, students now shift perspective: How can people live with floods, instead of fighting against them? Students discuss and simulate decisions about land use, restoration, and flood protection measures, learning that a balance between safety, ecology, and human well-being is possible.

KEYWORDS:

sustainable management, nature-based solutions, grey solutions, dam, dike, channelization, land use change

ACTIVITY – “BUILD OR BREATHE?” CHOOSING THE FUTURE OF A FLOODPLAIN

INSTRUCTIONS FOR STUDENTS:

Work in small groups (4–5 students). Each group represents a different stakeholder:

- Local residents
- Farmers
- Engineers
- Conservationists
- Municipality / decision-makers

The teacher presents a floodplain map or a real example (e.g., from the Danube) showing areas affected by flooding, farming, or urban expansion.

Groups discuss how to manage the floodplain:

- Should we build higher dikes and control the river (grey solution)?
- Should we combine protection and restoration (mixed/hybrid approach)?
- Should we restore the floodplain to a natural, multifunctional landscape (Nature-Based Solution)?

Each group writes or sketches their proposal and presents it briefly to the class.

After presentations, the class reflects on which solution offers the best balance between safety, biodiversity, and human well-being.

GUIDING QUESTIONS

- How can people adapt to the natural rhythm of floods rather than resist it?
- What are the advantages and disadvantages of each solution (Grey, Mixed, NbS)?
- Which solution helps both people and nature?
- How does this compare with how plants and animals adapt in floodplains?
- What would your “ideal floodplain of the future” look like?

TEACHER SUPPORT:

- Provide a simplified floodplain map or use a local case study.
- Use POSSIBLE SOLUTIONS FOR HUMAN PRESSURES ON RIVERS game from *People and aquatic ecosystem-Restore4Life* teaching materials.
- Facilitate discussion using the “adaptation lens”: Remind students that just as species adapt to change, humans must also adapt in order to use environmental resources sustainably, and to adapt to risks relating with floods and climate change.
- Optionally, show a short video or image of a restored Danube floodplain to visualize real examples of NbS.

5. EVALUATE – Testing knowledge through games (45 minutes)

AIM: To summarize and reflect on what students have learned about floodplain dynamics, adaptation, and human coexistence with nature.

Students consolidate their understanding through discussion, and creative expression, recognizing how floods, biodiversity, and people are interconnected in a living system. They express what they have learned and how their perception of floodplains has changed, reinforcing emotional connection and systems thinking.

KEYWORDS: emotional connection, system thinking, multifunctional floodplains, adaptation

ACTIVITY 1 – “LESSONS FROM A LIVING FLOODPLAIN” DISCUSSION

INSTRUCTIONS FOR STUDENTS:

Work in small groups to recall the main steps of your learning journey:

- What did you first think what is a floodplain?
- What surprised you most during the activities?
- Which animals, plants, or processes stood out to you?

Share your reflections with the class.

TEACHER SUPPORT:

- Encourage open sharing — there are no right or wrong answers.
- Write students’ keywords on the board to visualize collective learning.

ACTIVITY 2 – CREATIVE REFLECTION: “VOICES FROM THE FLOODPLAIN”

INSTRUCTIONS FOR STUDENTS:

Individually or in pairs, write or draw a short reflection titled “*If I were part of the floodplain...*” (e.g., a reed, a dragonfly, a fish, a frog, or even the river itself).

Express what you would feel, experience, or wish for the future of your home.

Share a few examples with the class.

TEACHER SUPPORT:

- Encourage creativity and empathy — this activity connects cognitive learning with emotional engagement.
- Display or collect student reflections as part of a “*The dynamic floodplain*” or class exhibition.
- Solutions and multifunctional floodplains by engaging in interactive games. By playing digital or project-developed games, they can explore real-world challenges, apply what they have learned, and reflect on the effectiveness of different strategies.

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FLOODPLAIN LIVING ENVIRONMENT

ANNEX 1

Floodplain dynamics is a result of the interplay of several processes that constantly shape floodplains, including the hydrological (water flow), geomorphological (landform changes), and ecological (life) changes over time. This dynamic is driven by a river's natural flooding cycles leading to the erosion and deposition of sediment, creating fertile soils and thus altering the physical landscape as well as vegetation and habitats for animals. Human activities, such as river regulation, can significantly impact these natural processes, leading to changes in flooding frequency, sediment transport, and ecosystem connectivity.

HYDROLOGICAL DYNAMICS

- **FLOODING REGIME:** Floodplains are characterized by periodic flooding. These floods bring water, nutrients, and sediments that sustain the floodplain ecosystem.
 - **Flooding Frequency** (how often floods occur),
 - **Flooding Duration** (how long water stays), and
 - **Flooding Extent** (how far floods spread)all influence vegetation patterns and soil development.
- **CONNECTIVITY:** Floodplains are laterally connected to the main river channel. During floods, water moves between the river and its floodplain, replenishing wetlands and also vertically recharging groundwater aquifers.

GEOMORPHOLOGICAL DYNAMICS

- **SEDIMENT TRANSPORT AND DEPOSITION:** Floods regularly erode parts of the floodplain, and also deposit new gravel or sand bars near river banks, and cover large floodplain areas with layers of fine sediment (silt, clay) that enrich the soil. Erosion and deposition continually reshape floodplain topography—creating sand bars, oxbow lakes, and meanders
- **CHANNEL MIGRATION:** Over time, rivers meanders move across their floodplains, cutting new channels and abandoning old ones. This migration maintains the dynamic equilibrium of the floodplain landscape and vegetation, providing habitats for pioneer species.

ECOLOGICAL DYNAMICS

- **VEGETATION SUCCESSION:** Floodplain areas of varying age and soil composition support different plant communities, depending on how often and how deeply they are flooded. After floods, pioneer species colonize bare sediments, followed by more established vegetation as soils stabilize.
- **HABITAT DIVERSITY:** The combination of water, sediment, and vegetation dynamics creates a mosaic of habitats—wetlands, short and tall herbaceous vegetation, backwaters, forests, and grasslands—supporting high biodiversity.

HUMAN AND CLIMATE INFLUENCES

- **RIVER REGULATION:** Channelization, dams, dikes and land-use changes alter floodplain dynamics by reducing river flow, flooding frequency, trapping sediment, and disrupting natural flows.
- **CLIMATE CHANGE:** Shifts in precipitation, river flow and temperature can modify flood regimes, leading to more frequent extreme floods or droughts.

REFERENCES

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FLOODPLAIN LIVING ENVIRONMENT

ANNEX 2

HOW ANIMALS AND PLANTS ADAPT TO THE DYNAMICS OF FLOODPLAINS

Floodplains are constantly changing due to flooding, erosion, and sediment deposition. Because of this, floodplains plants and animals must be able to survive both wet and dry conditions and adjust quickly to changes in water levels and habitats.

PLANT ADAPTATIONS

- **TOLERANCE TO FLOODING AND WATERLOGGING**
 - Floodplain plants (like reed, willows or poplars) can survive being submerged.
 - Many have aerenchyma — air spaces in their roots and stems that let oxygen move to submerged parts.
- **FAST GROWTH AFTER FLOODS**
 - After floods nutrient-rich silt is deposited, acting as fertilizer for quickly growing plants such as herbs, willows and poplars.
- **FLEXIBLE STEMS AND ROOTS**
 - Floodplain plants often have flexible stems that bend with flowing water, and are often able to grow new roots from bended or drifted stems.
- **SEED ADAPTATIONS**
 - Many species have seeds that float or can stay dormant until floodwaters recede, ensuring they germinate at the right time.

ANIMAL ADAPTATIONS

- **MOVEMENT AND MIGRATION**
 - Animals like fish and birds move with the floods — for example, fish breed in floodwaters, and birds follow flooded areas for food.
 - When water levels drop, they return to deeper or permanent water bodies.
- **BURROWING AND SEEKING SHELTER**
 - Amphibians, reptiles, and small mammals burrow into soil, move to higher ground or even climb trees in order to avoid being swept away or drowned during floods.
- **FLEXIBLE FEEDING AND BREEDING**
 - Many animals adapt their diet to the seasonal hydrological cycle.
 - Breeding times is often aligned to flood cycles, ensuring food for offspring.
- **RESILIENCE TO CHANGE**
 - Floodplain species are generally adapted to disturbance — they can recolonize new areas quickly when the river changes its course.

NR	SPECIES	ADAPTATION
1	White willow (<i>Salix alba</i>)	<p>Waterlogging resistance: White willow can survive prolonged periods of soil saturation.</p> <p>Aerenchyma tissues: Some willow roots have specialized air spaces that allow oxygen transport to submerged roots, preventing root suffocation during floods.</p> <p>Shallow and spreading roots: Adapted to unstable floodplain soils, allowing the tree to anchor itself while still being able to access oxygen and nutrients, roots also help stabilize riverbanks, reducing erosion.</p> <p>Water-dispersed seeds: White willow produces tiny seeds attached to cottony hairs that float on water, allowing colonization of newly formed floodplain areas.</p> <p>Rapid seedling establishment: Seeds germinate quickly on freshly deposited silt, which is ideal in constantly shifting floodplain landscapes.</p>
2	Cottonwood (<i>Populus alba</i>)	<p>Waterlogging resistance: <i>Populus alba</i> can survive periods of saturated soil or temporary flooding.</p> <p>Adapted root system: Shallow but widespread roots help in oxygen uptake in waterlogged soils.</p> <p>Fast growth: Takes advantage of nutrient-rich silt deposited during floods.</p> <p>Vegetative propagation: Can sprout from roots or broken branches, enabling recovery after flood damage.</p> <p>Wind-dispersed seeds: Seeds are small and attached to cottony hairs, allowing colonization of newly deposited silt along floodplains.</p> <p>Quick germination: Seeds establish rapidly in moist, freshly deposited soil, which is common in floodplains.</p> <p>Flexible stems and branches: Reduces risk of breakage during floods or strong currents.</p> <p>Ability to withstand partial uprooting: Trees can continue growing even if floodwaters partially expose or shift the roots.</p>

3	<p style="text-align: center;">Reed (<i>Phragmites australis</i>)</p>	<p>Extensive Rhizome Network (Vegetative Resilience) <i>Phragmites</i> has a massive rhizome system that spreads horizontally under the soil and can reach several meters in length. These rhizomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allow rapid colonization of newly flooded or exposed areas. • Store carbohydrates, providing energy reserves for regrowth after disturbance (e.g., drying, grazing, or flooding). • Anchor the plant in unstable, waterlogged sediments. <p>This enables the species to persist through cycles of inundation and drought—a core feature of floodplain dynamics.</p> <p>Tolerance to Variable Water Levels <i>Phragmites</i> tolerates both permanent flooding and temporary drought. It achieves this through:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A hollow stem and aerenchyma tissue that facilitate oxygen transport from shoots to submerged roots, allowing respiration even in anoxic sediments. • Ability to close stomata and reduce transpiration under drought or salinity stress. <p>This flexibility allows it to thrive across a wide hydrological gradient—from shallow water to periodically dry floodplains.</p> <p>High Growth Rate and Reproductive Output <i>Phragmites</i> shows rapid vertical growth (up to 4 m in one season), which allows it to outcompete other species as floodwaters rise. It reproduces:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Asexually, through rhizomes and stolons (dominant in floodplains). • Sexually, by producing large quantities of wind-dispersed seeds that can colonize newly deposited sediments. <p>This dual strategy ensures survival under unstable floodplain conditions where disturbance frequently resets vegetation.</p> <p>Physiological Tolerance to Environmental Stress Survives in a wide range of salinity, temperature, and nutrient conditions—important in floodplains where water quality fluctuates. Has efficient nutrient uptake mechanisms and can store nutrients in rhizomes for use during unfavourable periods. Exhibits phenotypic plasticity — the ability to adjust its growth form and physiology to local conditions (e.g., dense stands in nutrient-rich, flooded sites vs. sparser growth in drier areas).</p>
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4	Water Lily (<i>Nymphaea alba</i>)	<p>Large, broad leaves float on the water surface, allowing the plant to access sunlight even when water levels fluctuate. Floating leaves reduce competition for light with submerged plants.</p> <p>Flexible stems: Stems are long and flexible, connecting leaves to the roots anchored in the sediment. This flexibility allows the plant to adjust to changing water depths during floods or droughts.</p> <p>Anchored Root System: Roots are anchored in the sediment at the bottom of water bodies. This stabilizes the plant in soft, waterlogged soils typical of floodplains and prevents it from being washed away during floods.</p> <p>Aerenchyma Tissues: Stems and roots contain air-filled tissues (aerenchyma), which help transport oxygen from leaves to submerged roots. This adaptation allows survival in waterlogged or oxygen-poor soils.</p> <p>Floating seeds and vegetative reproduction: Seeds can float and disperse with water currents, colonizing newly formed ponds or floodplain areas.</p> <p>Rapid growth of rhizomes: Rhizomes (underground stems) allow the plant to spread vegetatively and quickly occupy available space after floods</p>
5	Great silver water beetle (<i>Hydrophilus piceus</i>)	<p>Air Storage: traps air under its wing cases (elytra) and on its body, allowing it to breathe underwater for extended periods.</p> <p>Swimming Adaptations: has long, flattened hind legs with hairs, functioning as paddles, which help it swim efficiently in flooded areas</p> <p>Mobility Between Water Bodies: Adult beetles can fly, enabling them to move to new ponds, ditches, or floodplain pools when their habitat dries out or becomes unsuitable.</p> <p>Ability to Exploit Temporary Pools: Larvae and adults can colonize newly formed or temporary water bodies created by floods, giving them access to new resources and reducing competition.</p> <p>Burrowing and Hiding: When water levels drop, <i>Hydrophilus piceus</i> can hide in mud or moist detritus, allowing it to survive until water returns.</p>
6	Duck mussel (<i>Anodonta anatina</i>)	<p>Burrowing Ability: Partially buried in sediment: Duck mussels live buried in soft floodplain substrates such as silt or sand, which protects them from strong currents during floods. Burrowing also reduces predation risk from fish and birds.</p> <p>Tolerance to Variable Water Conditions: Can survive in water with variable flow rates, from slow-moving floodplain pools to moderate river currents. Able to tolerate temporary reductions in water quality or oxygen levels that may occur during floods or sediment deposition.</p> <p>Filter feeder: Extracts plankton and organic particles from water, allowing it to take advantage of nutrient-rich waters created by flood events. Flexible feeding ensures survival even when water quality or flow changes.</p> <p>Robust, streamlined shell: Helps resist damage from sediment movement or debris carried during floods. Provides protection from predators.</p>

7	Painter's mussel (<i>Unio pictorum</i>)	<p>Burrowing and Substrate Attachment: Partially buried in sediment: The mussel lives buried in sand, silt, or mud, which protects it from strong currents and debris during floods. Burrowing also reduces predation from fish, birds, and other animals.</p> <p>Can survive in slow-moving or moderately flowing water, typical of floodplain channels and pools.</p> <p>Oxygen tolerance: Can withstand temporary decreases in oxygen levels that often occur during floods or sediment accumulation.</p> <p>Filter feeder: Extracts plankton, bacteria, and organic particles from the water. Floodwaters bring nutrient-rich sediments, providing abundant food and allowing <i>Unio pictorum</i> to thrive in dynamic environments.</p> <p>Reproductive Adaptations: Glochidia larvae: Larvae attach temporarily to fish gills or fins, allowing dispersal to new or newly formed habitats in the floodplain. This ensures colonization of shifting or newly deposited areas created by flooding.</p> <p>Thick, robust shell: Provides protection against physical disturbance from flowing water and sediment during floods. Protects against predation as well.</p>
8	European fire-bellied toad (<i>Bombina orientalis</i>)	<p>Breeding in shallow pools and floodplain ponds: The species lays eggs in temporary or permanent water bodies, taking advantage of seasonal flood-created habitats.</p> <p>Aquatic larvae (tadpoles): Develop in water, feeding on algae and detritus, and can survive in both permanent and ephemeral pools.</p> <p>Tolerance to Variable Water Levels: Can survive in water bodies with fluctuating depth caused by floods or drought. Capable of remaining near or under water during extreme conditions, reducing desiccation risk.</p> <p>High fecundity: Lays many eggs to ensure that some offspring survive in variable floodplain conditions.</p> <p>Rapid larval development: Tadpoles can develop quickly, enabling them to metamorphose before temporary pools dry up.</p> <p>Adults are mobile on land, able to move between ponds and water bodies if conditions change due to flooding or drying. This mobility allows colonization of newly formed floodplain habitats.</p> <p>Habitat Flexibility: Can inhabit both open floodplain wetlands and vegetated margins, allowing them to exploit different microhabitats created by floods.</p>

9	Dice snake (<i>Natrix tesellatta</i>)	<p>Excellent swimming ability: The snake has a streamlined body and strong muscles, allowing it to move efficiently in water during floods or while hunting aquatic prey.</p> <p>Hunting in water: Feeds primarily on fish and amphibians, which are abundant in floodplain pools and rivers, especially after floods</p> <p>Tolerance to Variable Water Levels: Can adapt to both deep and shallow waters, making use of newly formed floodplain channels and temporary ponds. Can escape rising water levels by moving to higher ground along floodplain banks.</p> <p>Egg-laying in safe, terrestrial locations: Female snakes lay eggs on flood-free soil or under vegetation, reducing the risk of eggs being washed away during floods.</p> <p>Timing of reproduction often coincides with stable water periods, ensuring hatchlings emerge when food is abundant.</p> <p>Ability to move on land: Dice snakes can migrate between water bodies if one becomes unsuitable due to flooding, drying, or sediment deposition. This mobility allows them to colonize new habitats created by floodplain dynamics.</p>
10	Common roach (<i>Rutilus rutilus</i>)	<p>Can live in both rivers and floodplain ponds, tolerating variable water depths.</p> <p>Able to exploit temporary floodplain habitats formed during high water events.</p> <p>Eurytopic species: Can tolerate variations in oxygen levels, temperature, and turbidity that often occur during floods or sediment deposition.</p> <p>Can survive in slow-moving, shallow, or murky water typical of floodplain pools.</p> <p>Spawning in shallow water or flooded areas: Eggs are laid on vegetation or substrate in areas newly inundated by floods.</p> <p>High fecundity: Produces a large number of eggs, increasing the likelihood of offspring survival in dynamic floodplain habitats.</p> <p>Rapid growth in nutrient-rich floodplain waters, which are enriched with silt and organic material after floods.</p> <p>Life cycle often synchronized with flood pulses, ensuring young fish develop when food and habitat are optimal.</p> <p>Can move between connected water bodies when floodwaters create new channels or when shallow pools dry up.</p> <p>Schooling behavior helps in avoiding predators and increases feeding efficiency in floodplain waters.</p>

11	Common bream (<i>Abramis brama</i>)	<p>Habitat Flexibility: Can tolerate slow-moving and stagnant waters, which are common in floodplain ponds and backwaters. Occupies both main river channels and temporary floodplain habitats, taking advantage of new or nutrient-rich areas created by flooding.</p> <p>Spawns in shallow, vegetated waters during spring and early summer when floodwaters create suitable habitats.</p> <p>High fecundity ensures that at least some offspring survive in unstable or changing environments.</p> <p>Can survive in turbid, low-oxygen waters that occur after floods or in floodplain ponds.</p> <p>Eurytopic nature allows it to cope with changes in temperature, turbidity, and oxygen levels.</p> <p>Rapid growth in nutrient-rich floodplain waters, which are enriched with silt and organic material after floods.</p> <p>Life cycle often synchronized with seasonal flooding, maximizing survival and resource use.</p> <p>Can move between connected water bodies via temporary channels created during floods, allowing colonization of newly formed habitats.</p>
12	Pike (<i>Esox Lucius</i>)	<p>Habitat Flexibility: Pike can thrive in main river channels, backwaters, and temporary floodplain pools. When rivers flood, they migrate into inundated floodplains to feed and spawn, taking advantage of abundant prey and vegetation cover. Can tolerate a wide range of temperatures, oxygen levels, and turbidity, typical of floodplain systems.</p> <p>Reproductive Adaptations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spawning in flooded areas: Pike spawn in shallow, vegetated floodplain zones during spring floods. The eggs attach to grasses and reeds in newly flooded areas. • Timing with flood cycles: Spawning coincides with seasonal flooding, ensuring that larvae hatch in safe, food-rich floodplain waters. • High fecundity: Produces thousands of eggs to ensure population survival despite unstable floodplain conditions. <p>Mobility:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pike are strong swimmers and can move easily between connected water bodies. • Seasonal migrations allow them to colonize new floodplain habitats or retreat to deeper channels during drought or receding floods. <p>Physiological and Behavioral Tolerance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tolerates low oxygen levels, enabling survival in stagnant floodplain pools after floodwaters recede. • Can remain motionless for long periods, conserving energy when conditions are poor. <p>Juvenile Adaptations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Young pike use vegetated floodplain shallows for shelter and feeding, avoiding predation and benefiting from abundant small prey. • Rapid early growth allows juveniles to outgrow predation risk quickly.

13	Grey heron (<i>Ardea cinerea</i>)	<p>Feeding Adaptations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Long legs: Allow the heron to wade in shallow and variable waters, accessing prey in flooded areas or exposed mudflats. • Long, sharp bill: Perfectly adapted for spearing fish, frogs, and invertebrates, which become abundant during floods. • Slow, stealthy hunting behaviour: The heron can stand motionless for long periods, waiting for prey to approach — an efficient strategy in changing water levels. • Flexible feeding sites: Can forage in rivers, floodplain pools, ditches, or temporarily flooded fields, depending on water availability. <p>Habitat Flexibility:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highly mobile: Moves easily between different parts of the floodplain as conditions change — for example, retreating to permanent waters during droughts or exploiting temporary pools during floods. • Generalist species: Can adapt to a wide range of aquatic environments, from shallow wetlands to deep river margins. <p>Reproductive Adaptations:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nesting in trees or reedbeds above flood level: Builds large stick nests (often in colonies) in safe, elevated sites to avoid flooding. • Colony nesting (heronries): Provides protection from predators and ensures efficient use of prime nesting areas close to floodplain feeding sites. • Reproductive timing: Breeds in spring when floodwaters recede, ensuring food is abundant for chicks.
14	Cormorant (<i>Phalacrocorax carbo</i>)	<p>Aquatic Feeding Adaptations</p> <p>Excellent divers: Streamlined bodies and strong webbed feet make them powerful underwater swimmers, allowing them to chase fish even in fast-flowing or flooded waters.</p> <p>Hooked bill: Helps them grasp slippery fish, the main prey in floodplain habitats.</p> <p>Dense bones: Reduce buoyancy, enabling them to dive deep and stay submerged while hunting.</p> <p>Habitat versatility: Cormorants can use a variety of water bodies — main river channels, floodplain lakes, temporary ponds, or inundated forests — depending on water level and prey availability.</p> <p>Adaptation to fluctuating water levels: They readily move between habitats as floodwaters rise or recede, exploiting newly flooded areas rich in fish.</p> <p>Breeding flexibility: Can adjust breeding timing and locations depending on flood conditions and food supply.</p>
15	White stork (<i>Ciconia ciconia</i>)	<p>Long legs and a long bill: The stork has long red legs and a pointed beak, enabling walking through shallow water/muddy ground and probing or grabbing prey</p> <p>The stork often builds nests on tall structures (trees, rooftops, chimneys, poles) that overlook open terrain and near feeding grounds (wet meadows, floodplains, marshes).</p> <p>Because floodplains generate pulses of invertebrate, amphibian, small-vertebrate availability (due to inundation, drying, sediment exposure), the stork's opportunistic diet allows it to rapidly take advantage of these pulses.</p>
16	Common kingfisher (<i>Alcedo atthis</i>)	<p>Nictitating membrane: A transparent eyelid protects the eyes underwater while maintaining vision during dives.</p> <p>Timing of breeding: Usually breeds after the main flood season, when water levels stabilize and food is plentiful for chicks.</p>

17	Eurasian otter (<i>Lutra lutra</i>)	<p>Dense, waterproof fur: Consists of two layers — a soft insulating underfur and a water-repellent outer layer — keeping the body dry and warm in cold floodwaters.</p> <p>Nostrils and ears close underwater, preventing water entry during dives.</p> <p>Whiskers (vibrissae): Highly sensitive and used to detect prey in murky floodwaters, where visibility is poor.</p>
18	Eurasian beaver (<i>Castor fiber</i>)	<p>Morphological adaptation</p> <p>Webbed hind feet: Aid in swimming and maneuvering efficiently in floodwaters.</p> <p>Flattened, scaly tail: Serves as a rudder for swimming, a fat storage organ, and a warning signal when slapped on water.</p> <p>Sharp, ever-growing incisors: Adapted for cutting wood and vegetation, enabling dam and lodge construction.</p> <p>Dense, waterproof fur: Keeps the body insulated and dry during prolonged swimming and working in flooded areas.</p> <p>Can stay submerged for 15-20 minutes, allowing safe movement during floods or predator avoidance.</p> <p>Nostrils and ears close underwater; eyes adapted to see both above and below the surface.</p>

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Restore4Life

RESTORING WETLANDS
FOR A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE

FLOODPLAIN LIVING ENVIRONMENT

WORKSHEET: FLOODPLAIN HEROES

PURPOSE OF THE ACTIVITY

Players take on the role of plants or animals living in a floodplain. Their goal is to **survive and thrive** over multiple “floodplain events” by using species-specific adaptations. In this game you will find out how adaptations help organisms cope with **flooding, drought, and habitat changes**.

SETUP THE GAME

- 1 Prepare the map and the cards (Species cards, Adaptation cards and Event cards will be cut individually before starting the game).
- 2 Each player chooses a Species card.
- 3 Place all species cards in their preferred starting zones (e.g., fish in river, reed on river bank).
- 4 Shuffle the Event cards and choose one.

ROUNDS OF PLAY

- 1 The game is played over 5–6 rounds, each representing a change in the floodplain environment.
- 2 At the start of each round, draw an Event card. Example of events:
 - Flood: Low-lying areas underwater for 1 turn
 - Drought: Wetlands dry up, food sources decrease
 - Erosion: Some zones disappear, species must move
 - Sediment deposition: New fertile areas appear
- 3 Players decide how their species responds choosing an adaptation:
 - Move to higher ground
 - Spread seeds or offspring
 - Burrow or hide
 - Take advantage of new resources

SURVIVAL CHECKS

After each event, check survival:

- If a species cannot use its adaptations to cope, it **loses a life point** (1–3 life points depending on species resilience).
- If life points drop to zero, the species is **eliminated**.

SCORING

Points are earned for:

- Surviving an event
- Successfully reproducing or spreading seeds/offspring
- Occupying new zones created by sediment deposition

Bonus points for **creative use of adaptations** (teacher or group decides).

WINNING THE GAME:

After the final round, the species with the **highest survival points** is the “Floodplain Hero”.

Print double-sided: SPECIES CARDS

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SALIX ALBA

PHRAGMITES SP.

NYMPHAEA ALBA

PLOPUS ALBA

*HYDROPHILUS
PICEUS*

*ANODONTA
ANATINA*

*UNIO
PICTORUM*

*BOMBINA
BOMBINA*

*NATRIX
TESELLATTA*

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RUTILUS RUTILUS

ABRAMIS BRAMA

ESOX LUCIUS

ARDEA CINEREA

PHALACROCORAX

CICONIA CICONIA

ALCEDO ATTHIS

LUTRA LUTRA

CASTOR FIBER

ADAPTATIONS
CARDS

ADAPTATIONS CARDS

FLOATING SEEDS

AERENCHYMA
TISSUES

WATERLOGGING
RESISTANCE

FLEXIBLE FEEDING

BURROWING

FAST GROWTH

DENSE, WATERPROOF
FUR

FLATTENED,
SCALY TAIL

WEBBED HIND FEET

ADAPTATIONS
CARDS

ADAPTATIONS CARDS

LONG BILL

LONG LEGS

NOSTRILS AND EARS
CLOSE UNDERWATER

BREEDING
FLEXIBILITY

OPPORTUNISTIC
DIET

COLONY NESTING

EGGS ATTACH TO
GRASSES

HIGH FECUNDITY

TOLERANCE
TO VARIABLE
WATER LEVELS

ADAPTATIONS
CARDS

ADAPTATIONS CARDS

BURROWING ABILITY

OXYGEN TOLERANCE

RAPID LARVAL
DEVELOPMENT

QUICK GERMINATION

ANCHORED ROOT
SYSTEM

AIR STORAGE

LARGE, BROAD
FLOATING LEAVES

FLEXIBLE STEAMS

EXTENSIVE RHIZOME
NETWORK

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EVENT CARDS

FLOOD

DROUGHT

EROSION

SEDIMENT
DEPOSITION